

Karina Phoenix Leigh Helena's Two Cents

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Like the leaders of linguistic change,
nonconformity has easily become a propensity.

In pronunciation mainly:
dint from didn't, comftably for comfortably, histry from history.

It facilitates speech...

Prescriptivism in construction, however
should be brought to the fore
along with substance in speech
to at least elude fossilization
and perhaps ease students' academic writing,
which becomes grueling
in higher education
where correct usage is rendered imperative.